

Application of solvent-based dissolution for the recycling of polyvinylchloride flooring waste containing restricted phthalate plasticizers

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ABSTRACT

The applicability of a new recycling method for extracting contaminants from polymers, dissolution-based recycling, was tested on a polyvinylchloride equipped with diethylhexyl phthalate, benzylbutyl phthalate, diisobutyl phthalate, di-n-butyl phthalate, originating from post-consumer flooring waste. Due to European restrictions on these ortho-phthalate diester-based plasticizers, the mechanical recycling of plasticized polyvinylchloride is no longer feasible. In this study, we have shown that dissolution and consecutive purification of the polymer eliminate 99.9 % of diethylhexyl phthalate's initial concentration at the laboratory scale. The impact of different process parameters, e.g., temperature, agitation, and extraction kinetics, have been tested. The findings were transferred to a technical scale of 5 kg/d, using a multi-step extraction in counter-flow mode. An elimination of 99.4 % of diethylhexyl phthalate initial concentration has been achieved, which fulfills legal requirements. These promising results showed the technical feasibility and served as a preliminary stage for further up-scaling to technical readiness level 6.

1. Introduction

Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) is one of the most essential plastics in Europe. With a market size of 5.3 million tons in 2022, the third most crucial plastic represents 9.1 % of the European plastic market (PlasticsEurope, 2023). PVC has many applications in the building, packaging, and pharmaceutical industries, but 71 % of the PVC produced in Europe is used in the building and construction sector, particularly for long-life products such as piping, window frames, and flooring (Conversio Market and Strategy GmbH, 2018). The diverse applications of PVC reflect the different formulations of auxiliary materials or additives, including stabilizers, lubricants, fillers, modifiers, and plasticizers in the case of plasticized PVC (PVC-P). PVC flooring mainly comprises paste-PVC (28–70 %), chalk (0–60 %), epoxidized fatty acid esters (0–3 %), phthalate plasticizer (10–40 %), and stabilizer (0–3 %) (Bonau, 1992; Schiller, 2015).

The main role of plasticizers is to lower the glass transition temperature (T_g), and by this, improve PVC processing and the final properties of PVC-P products. They increase the distance between the polymer chains and loosen the dipolar forces (Erythropel et al., 2016; Wypych, 2012). Common phthalate plasticizers in PVC floorings include

diisononyl phthalate (DINP), di-isoheptyl phthalate (DIHP), benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP) and di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP), with the latter playing the most significant role by far. In 1999, ~1.1 million tons of plasticizers were produced in Western Europe, 42 % of which (460,000 tons) was DEHP (European Commission, 2000; European Chemicals Agency, 2010). Because phthalate plasticizers such as DEHP do not bind covalently to the PVC polymer, these substances are emitted into the indoor environments through abrasion, leaching, and outgassing (Clausen et al., 2004; Clausen et al., 2007; Weschler and Fong, 1986). Environmental compartments, plants, animals, and humans can absorb phthalate plasticizers (Oehlmann et al., 2009). Previous studies have shown that, in particular, house dust plays a significant role in human uptake by ingestion when the dust is in contact with plasticized PVC flooring (Shinohara and Uchino, 2020). Higher concentrations of DEHP in house dust (34 µg/mg) are associated with asthma and allergies in children (Bornehag et al., 2004). Toxicological studies on animals have shown that DEHP is toxic in rodents, particularly affecting the reproductive organs and liver (Zarean et al., 2016; Li et al., 2014). In 2008, these reprotoxic properties resulted in the addition of DEHP to the REACH candidate list (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals), a European register for chemicals that require

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regulation (Geraghty, 2008). Without authorization, DEHP has been prohibited in the EU since 21 February 2015 (European Commission 2/17/2011). Besides DEHP, other phthalates like dibutyl phthalate (DBP), benzylbutyl phthalate (BBP), and diisobutyl phthalate (DIBP) with a similar risk profile have also been restricted by REACH legislation (Wagner and Schlummer, 2020). The legal threshold for a non-authorized application of phthalate plasticizers in consumer products is currently 0.1 % (w/w) (Geraghty, 2008; Wagner and Schlummer, 2020). Because recent human biomonitoring studies revealed the increasing presence of mono-n-hexyl phthalate (MnHexP, a metabolite from di-n-hexyl phthalate, classified as reprotoxic >60 µg/L) in children's urine from 2017 to 2021 (Umweltbundesamt, 2023) (Umweltbundesamt 3/25/2024), the ECHA consider a restriction in combination with an authorization for all ortho-phthalates with substituents of medium chain length (C4-C6) (European Chemicals Agency, 2021).

Although PVC products have a longer life (in some cases more than 80 years) than other polymers, a considerable amount of waste PVC is generated at their end of life. In Germany alone, the PVC waste stream from building and construction amounted to 0.25 million tons in 2017, 99 % of which was recovered (72 % energy recovery, 27 % material recycling), while the rest went to landfill (Conversio Market and Strategy GmbH, 2018). Energetic recovery of PVC targets power generation, which is achieved by adding PVC to the domestic waste in incineration plants. Although most PVC is recovered this way, much less energy is recovered than required during PVC manufacturing (Perugini et al., 2005; Bund für Umwelt und Naturschutz e.V., 2010). Additionally, the chlorine released from PVC during combustion also contributes to the formation of hydrochloric acid, which takes part in corrosion mechanisms and can reduce the lifetime of incineration equipment (Buekens and Cen, 2011). Several recycling strategies exist for PVC, of which mechanical recycling is the most relevant. Approximately 37 % of waste PVC (post-industrial + post-consumer) was recovered via this route in Germany in 2017 (Conversio Market and Strategy GmbH, 2018). Mechanical recycling entails collecting, sorting, grinding, and re-melting (Sadat-Shojai and Bakhshandeh, 2011). The mechanical properties are deteriorating since PVC tends to photochemical and thermal degradation during its lifetime and (re-)processing. Therefore, recycled material is usually mixed with virgin-grade polymer, additives, and fillers (Braun, 2002). Another obstacle to this recycling method is the inefficient purification, which leaves residual contaminants such as phthalate plasticizers or heavy metal stabilizers.

Dissolution-based recycling (DBR) processes constitute another promising recycling technique for PVC. Here, the PVC is dissolved in a selective solvent, separated from foreign material (e.g., foreign polymer, metal, minerals) by filtration, and subsequently precipitated. The used solvent is recovered and brought back into the recycling process. A significant advantage of DBR techniques is that the macromolecular structure of the PVC stays intact, and by this, virgin-like qualities are achievable (Niessner, 2022). Dissolution of PVC has been commercialized as Vinyloop®, Polyloop, and the CreaSolv® Process. The former had to be abandoned in 2018 because banned phthalates could not be separated (Plasteurope.com 8/14/2018). Currently, the process Polyloop and CreaSolv are preparing for commercialized scale-up. In the modular and mobile Polyloop process, the recycling focuses on flexible PVC composites, which don't contain banned plasticizers (Polyloop). Contrarily to the mentioned techniques, with the CreaSolv® Process, it is possible to remove legacy additives (e.g., phthalates, heavy metals, brominated flame retardants). This process showed good cleaning success for various waste inputs and has proven its cleaning potential in different studies with polymers other than PVC (Schlummer et al., 2006; Schlummer et al., 2016). The industrial scale for the recycling of brominated polystyrene with this technology has been realized at the PSLoop plant in Terneuzen (NL) (PSLoop).

This study demonstrates the applicability of the DBR technique for phthalate-contaminated PVC flooring. The aim is to generate a PVC

recyclate compliant with legal thresholds (< 0.1 % DEHP, BBP, DIBP, DBP content) without authorization through the REACH committee. Various parameters (temperature, stirring speed, time, material exchange principle) are tested for optimization of the phthalate extraction. The main compound of phthalate plasticizers, DEHP, is monitored in different process unit operations. GC-FID assesses product qualities of intermediate and final products.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

For this study, a representative PVC flooring waste was used. The ground PVC flooring waste chips originated from demolition sites and were provided by a German PVC recycler. This post-consumer waste was a mixture of different PVC flooring from various manufacturers and production periods (which are unknown) and was therefore contaminated with phthalate plasticizer.

The process liquids, solvent, and precipitant were provided by our collaboration partner, CreaCycle GmbH, in Grevenbroich (Germany). Solvent and precipitant were explicitly selected for the dissolution and precipitation of PVC. According to the GHS (Globally Harmonized System), both liquids are non-hazardous and not subject to labeling according to GHS. The CreaSolv® is a registered trademark of the CreaCycle GmbH, Grevenbroich. The composition of CreaSolv® formulations is the intellectual property of CreaCycle GmbH and cannot be disclosed here.

2.2. Recycling unit operation

Fig. 1 shows the general block flow diagram of the DBR for PVC flooring waste, in which the phthalates plasticizer is extracted stepwise. We carried out the individual process steps as described below.

2.2.1. Dissolution and filtration

The PVC flooring waste chips were dissolved in a PVC-selective CreaSolv® solvent at temperatures below the flash point of the solvent (lab scale: beaker and magnetic stirrer with heating function from Heidolph; technical scale: double-walled mixing vessel), undissolved matter (cellulose-like material, foreign polymer, minerals) was separated using a candle filter with a mesh width of 100 µm (technical scale) or a kitchen sieve with a mesh width of 1 mm (laboratory scale). Centrifugation (8000 rpm, 10 min, Sorvall RC 6 Plus) was performed to separate chalk and for mass balance analysis at the laboratory scale.

2.2.2. Precipitation and post-extraction

After filtration, a precipitant was added to the PVC solution (θ < flash point of solvent) to change the polarity of the liquid medium. The PVC precipitated as a dispersed polymer gel, whereas the phthalate plasticizer was distributed between gel and extract phases. Two process variants were investigated to further reduce the phthalate concentration (Fig. 1). In variant 1, the dissolution and precipitation of the PVC were repeated until a legal threshold of phthalates was reached. At variant 2, the wet polymer gel is repeatedly rinsed with an extracting agent consisting of solvent and precipitant, allowing extraction without redissolution.

2.2.3. Separation

Separating phases (gel, extract) was carried out by a Buchner funnel under vacuum at lab scale and suction lance at technical scale. The dry matter of the moist PVC gel was increased by compacting the gel using a press on a technical scale (stainless steel juicer). After pressing, the extract containing the phthalates is removed so that the PVC gel has a lower phthalate concentration.

2.2.4. Drying

Solvent and precipitant are evaporated from the PVC gel through

Fig. 1. DBR process for contaminated PVC flooring. There are two processes for extracting phthalates: Process variants 1 (green) and 2 (orange). One of the two process variants is repeated until the legal limit value has been reached.

convective drying by a fluid-bed dryer (lab scale: Retsch TG 200; technical scale: In-house construction Lömi GmbH). Dispersed PVC grains are recovered in a powder form.

2.2.5. Solvent regeneration

Phthalate-loaded extracts are distilled to separate solvent and phthalates. The regenerated solvent can be re-used for dissolution of PVC waste and extraction of phthalates. The separated plasticizers are collected in the distillation sump and can be further processed or disposed of following regulations.

2.3. Characterization of input, intermediate, and final products

The efficiency of the recovery process was determined by testing the product characteristics using several analytical methods, as described below. As the waste is expected to be very inhomogeneous, the PVC chips were taken from different locations in the sample container (800 kg Octabin), mixed, and dissolved three times to have an error estimation in further analysis. All data in the result chapter are mean values.

2.3.1. X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF)

XRF was used to determine the levels of calcium (Ca) originating from the calcium carbonate filler (chalk). The PVC solution and the moist PVC precipitate were filled into Prolene® lined PTFE cuvettes and analyzed using a Spectro X-Lab 2000 instrument (Spectro, Kleve, Germany). Quantification based on the calibration provided by Spectro.

2.3.2. Gas chromatography with flame ionization detector (GC-FID)

The phthalate content of the PVC gel and extract was determined by GC-FID using a Thermo Quest Trace GC 2000 Series instrument equipped with a DB 1 MS column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm). The injector was operated at 290 °C in split mode, and the FID detector was operated at 320 °C. For sample preparation, we dissolved 0.5 g of the dried PVC precipitate in 12.5 mL of tetrahydrofuran and 500 ng internal standard (di-cyclohexyl phthalate (DCHP) 10 μg/mL) followed by precipitation with 37.5 mL ethanol. 1.0 mL of the extracts from the PVC precipitate was passed through a 0.2 μm nylon filter before analysis. Extracts obtained from the recycling process were directly diluted by a factor of 100 using toluene and doted with 100 ng of internal standard (IS) (100 μL extract + 10 μL IS + 9.9 mL toluene). An aliquot of the diluted extract was passed through a 0.2 μm nylon filter before analysis. Chromatographic raw data were analyzed using Chromeleon software.

Quantification of di-ethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP), dibutyl phthalate (DBP), benzylbutyl phthalate (BBP), and diisobutyl phthalate (DIBP) was based on an internal standard method based on calibration curves varying the target phthalate concentrations from 1 to 1000 μg/mL. Limits of detection were determined based on the smallest standard of the calibration curve and range from 33 to 59 mg kg⁻¹ sample.

2.3.3. Gas chromatography with mass spectrometry coupling (GC-MS)

GC-MS (GC-17A injecting 2 μL in splitless mode coupled with QP5000, Shimadzu) was used to identify the total plasticizer in the waste sample. GC separation was performed on a Zebron ZB-50 column (Phenomenex) with the dimension of 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm, and the column temperature was programmed from 90 °C (2 min) to 320 °C (10 min) with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The phthalates BBP, DBP, DEHP, DIBP, di-isooheptyl phthalate (DIHP), di-isononyl phthalate (DINP), and di-n-octyl phthalate (DNOP), as well as the di-ethylhexyl adipate (DEHA), are detected (Appendix 1). From a measuring solution used for GC-FID, 250 μL is made up to 25 mL with ethanol in a volumetric flask. This dilution by a factor of 100 was necessary to account for the higher sensitivity of the MS. 1.0 mL of the measuring solution is added to a GC vial. Deuterated DEHP (DEHP-3,4,5,6-d4) is used as an internal standard at a concentration of 1000 ppm, added to the measuring solution in the vial (5 μL). One target fragment was used to select ion monitoring (SIM) mode for phthalate identification. Quantification was based on m/z = 149.1 for phthalic diethyl ester and m/z = 153.1 for the internal standard (Zimmermann et al., 2012).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of PVC flooring waste

First, the PVC flooring waste components were determined to quantify the initial amount of DEHP and other phthalate plasticizers in the samples. As shown in Fig. 2b, the proportion of PVC in the waste accounted for 59 %. The other components comprised 28 % chalk (CaCO₃), 3 % insoluble cellulose-like components (fibers), 9 % plasticizers (DEHP, DINP, BBP, DIHP, DBP, DEHA, DIBP, DNOP, determined by GC-MS; Appendix 1). Among the phthalate plasticizers, DEHP was the most prominent, representing 43 % of the total plasticizer content (4 % in flooring waste) (Fig. 2b).

These results are consistent with previous reports of the composition of PVC flooring and the market share of DEHP of 43 % in 1999 related to

Fig. 2. a) Shredded post-consumer PVC chips from demolition site; b) distribution of PVC flooring waste components and share of the different plasticizers of the total plasticizer content in PVC flooring waste determined by GC-MS.

plasticizer consumption (Bonau, 1992; Schiller, 2015; ECHA, 2010). Because DEHP and BBP exceed the threshold concentration of the REACH directive (> 0.1 %) in the PVC flooring waste, it cannot be recycled by conventional recycling processes (grinding and re-melting or mixing) without authorization. Therefore, we tested the DBR technique for recovering PVC, including separating the plasticizers.

3.2. Purification concept

Dissolving and precipitation methods separate the restricted phthalates from the PVC polymer. In Fig. 3, the polymer is first dissolved in a solvent at elevated temperature. The polymer clusters are expanded in this step, and non-covalently bound additives are released into the medium. A dispersion is thus formed. By adding an anti-solvent to the mixture, the polarity of the solvent is changed, so the polymer is formed into a cluster again and precipitates.

Contrarily, the dispersed additives are distributed in the different phases depending on their polarity. In the case of this study, three phases are emerging: precipitated polymer, solvent, and anti-solvent. The

phthalates are distributed in two (solvent, precipitated polymer); since the anti-solvent is polar, no phthalates could be detected in this phase. The first purification step is achieved by separating the precipitated polymer (gel) from the extract (solvent, anti-solvent). Depending on the restricted phthalates' initial concentration, the first purification step might not be sufficient for compliance with the legal threshold (for restricted phthalates > 1000 ppm). In this case, post-extraction must follow. Here, a mixture of solvent and anti-solvent is added to the (partially purified) polymer gel. Because of the presence of an anti-solvent, the polymer won't dissolve, but phthalates are extracted into the solvent/anti-solvent mixture due to better solubility. Repeated dissolution and precipitation can be applied as an alternative approach to removing the phthalates. Phthalate-loaded extracts are purified by repeating re-dissolving and precipitation until the legal threshold is reached.

Fig. 3. Sequence of the process steps to eliminate restricted substances via dissolution and precipitation of polymers.

3.3. Factors influencing the purification efficiency of extraction via precipitation

Here, we show the factors influencing the precipitation efficiency. In Fig. 4a, the repeated dissolving and precipitation of the PVC was carried out under the standard parameters described in 2.2. At each re-dissolution of PVC-gel, the PVC content was adjusted to the same level, and re-precipitation was performed by the same amount of anti-solvent. Concentrations of DEHP in the extract phase and the precipitated PVC-gel were determined. Based on these two pairs of values, partition coefficients K were determined after each purification step, which indicates the ratio of the equilibrium concentrations of DEHP in the solvent-rich and PVC-rich phases:

$$K = c(\text{DEHP})_{\text{Extract}} / c(\text{DEHP})_{\text{PVC gel}}$$

Comparing the DEHP concentrations of both phases after each precipitation, it is apparent that there is an equal distribution between both phases (including the measurement uncertainty), which is also manifested by the partition coefficient K close to 1.0. The concentration of DEHP in PVC after each precipitation is reduced exponentially so that the final DEHP concentration after four precipitations is below the legal threshold of 1000 ppm (related to dried PVC recyclate). Although the liquid (solvent) to solid (PVC) ratio was the same before each precipitation step, the ratio of extract to PVC gel after each precipitation varied (Fig. 4a). With every precipitation step, the ratio $m(\text{extract})/m(\text{PVC-gel})$ rises, but the DEHP concentration in the PVC gel is reduced. Thus, the phthalate concentration in the PVC gel supports solvent absorption. In general, in an extraction process, it is aimed that most of the extractable substance is distributed in the extract phase so that $K \geq 1$ and most of the solvent is available as a free phase (ratio $m(\text{extract})/m(\text{PVC-gel}) \geq 1$). Loaded solvent as a free phase can be easily separated by decantation, while loaded solvent enclosed in the PVC-gel will be removed by evaporation in downstream processing, which leads to a

higher DEHP concentration in the PVC. K and the extract and PVC-gel ratio represent a parameter for the extraction success. The higher K and the higher the ratio, the better the extraction.

In the next step, we tested the effect of different parameters on the physical appearance of the PVC precipitate. We found that PVC precipitates differ in shape and structure depending on the stirring method or stirring speed during the precipitation. Rapid stirring with a magnetic bar produced a finely-grained PVC precipitate in the suspension. In contrast, slow folding of the precipitant with a spoon produced a large clump of PVC precipitate (Appendix 2). The efficiency of DEHP extraction was tested under an equal amount of precipitant and temperature for both precipitates.

For further observation in Fig. 4b, only the precipitation (first pair of bars) shall be considered. Here, the DEHP concentration in the dried PVC gel is applied to show the significant difference between the precipitation methods. Here, the partition coefficient K is at both methods by 1.4, which means an equal distribution in extract and PVC-gel is reached. Considering the ratio $m(\text{Extract})/m(\text{PVC gel})$ of both methods, the PVC clump has a significantly lower ratio of 0.3 compared to the fine-grained PVC with a ratio of 1.1. The PVC clump thus traps a lot of loaded solvent, resulting in poor extraction efficiency. Consequently, the precipitation with low agitation, which produces a PVC clump, is undesirable and has not been investigated further.

3.4. Factors influencing the purification efficiency of post-treatment of precipitated PVC

In this chapter, factors influencing post-extraction are analyzed. Starting from the last attempt to vary the shape of the precipitant (Appendix 2), post-extraction was applied to both PVC gels for further extractions. Therefore, the solvent and precipitant were mixed with the PVC gel for both post-extractions in the same ratio while stirring with a magnetic bar on a heat plate. As shown in Fig. 4b, the DEHP concentration in the fine-grained PVC gel is lower in the following two post-

Fig. 4. a) Repeated dissolution and precipitation of PVC-containing plasticizer with K and mass ratio of extract and precipitated PVC gel phases; b) comparison of DEHP conc. (in dry matter) in different PVC precipitants with K and ratio of $m(\text{extract})/m(\text{PVC-gel})$ of the two different methods; c) Temperature impact on DEHP concentration after each extraction step in the extract; d) time dependency of post-extraction 1-3 with a marking of 2.5 min, 5 min, and 15 min.

extraction steps than in the clumpy gel. The greater surface of the fine-grained PVC gel and shorter diffusion pathways result in a greater exchange of solvent and gel. The concentration gradient ($\partial c/\partial x$) between gel and solvent is higher ($c(\text{DEHP})_{\text{PVC}} = 27,000 \mu\text{g/g}$; $c(\text{DEHP})_{\text{solvent}} = 0 \mu\text{g/g}$; t_0 ; x_0), and this results in a more significant matter flow (J) of DEHP from high concentration in the gel to low concentration in the solvent (first Fick's law):

$$J = -D(\partial c/\partial x)$$

The phenomena of greater diffusion of DEHP into the solvent with finer particles can also be seen in K. This is higher in the finer material. However, the $m(\text{gel})/m(\text{extract})$ ratio is similar.

Further, we tested the influence of temperature on the DEHP extraction. As depicted in Fig. 4c, DEHP concentration in the extract depends on temperature in the first post-extraction. Accordingly, the extraction is more efficient, the higher the temperature. This trend is visible but weaker in the second post-extraction. However, between 70 °C and 90 °C, the DEHP concentration in the extract remains at the same level. Here, too, the observations can be derived with the diffusion law. The matter flow (J) depends on the diffusion coefficient D , which can be described with the Stokes-Einstein-equation for liquids:

$$D = k_B * T/6 * \pi * \eta * R_0$$

Therefore, the diffusion coefficient D increases with increasing temperature, and thus, the matter flow J . In the second post-extraction, the DEHP concentration in the PVC gel is lower than in the previous steps; hence, the concentration gradient ($\partial c/\partial x$) between both phases decreases, slowing the matter flow J . This means the first post-extraction should be performed at 90 °C to maximize the diffusion rate. Further extractions can be performed at lower temperatures (70 °C-90 °C) if this is relevant from an energy perspective.

Next, we tested the influence of time on the DEHP extraction. Thereby, time curves of the post-extractions 1–3 of one batch were generated at 80 °C and rapid stirring. The experiment generated the extract data, and the data for the PVC gel was generated using back calculation. At the same time, the absolute mass of DEHP has been subtracted after each extraction step. Fig. 4d shows a DEHP increase in the extract and DEHP depletion in the PVC gel as a function of time.

In Fig. 4d, it is apparent that in the three post-extraction the DEHP concentrations from PVC gel and extract approached each other within 15 min when the experiment was terminated. In the first post-extraction, the DEHP concentration changes steadily between the 1st and 15th minute, and the diffusion of DEHP into the extract slows down in the second and third post-extraction. Thus, the partition coefficient K approaches the value one the longer the system is stirred. In the above paragraph, we described that the better the extraction efficiency, the higher the K . Consequently, 15 min or longer per extraction step is necessary to successfully eliminate DEHP in the PVC waste. Taking into account, that in an upscaled process the time required for filling, stirring and emptying a large scale extraction tank the extraction time appears to be in a realistic order of magnitude and does not represent a bottleneck in the process. Based on the legal limit value for DEHP of 1000 ppm, this

Table 1

DEHP elimination after each purification (starting from the initial concentration of 54,460 ppm in the waste) and the residual DEHP concentration after each purification step in the PVC recycle.

Purification step	DEHP reduction in purification step/%	Total DEHP reduction/%	Residual DEHP conc./ppm
Precipitation	49	49	27,775
1. Post-extraction	25	87	6899
2. Post-extraction	26	97	1808
3. Post-extraction	26	99	465

is reached after three post-extraction steps of 15 min each (Table 1). This enabled an elimination rate of 99 % after 45 min post-extraction time plus the time for precipitation (Table 1).

The extraction within the DBR technique can be varied in three different methods: “resolve and precipitate,” “cross-flow,” and “counter-flow.” The phthalate-loaded extract is removed using the method “resolve and precipitate” after initial precipitation of the PVC solution at 80 °C. Then, the polymer gel is resolved in solvent again and precipitated (80 °C) after entirely dissolving. This procedure is repeated until a desired phthalate concentration has been reached. In the “cross-flow” method, the polymer gel is not re-dissolved after initial precipitation and removal of extract. Instead, a mixture of solvent and precipitate is added to the polymer gel, which is stirred by rapid movement (80 °C, 5 min). The precipitant in this mixture avoids the re-dissolving of the polymer in the solvent but also allows the migration of phthalates into the extract. The third method, “counter-flow,” is distinguished from the previous method in re-using the solvent or extract from previous extraction steps. In Fig. 5a, the results of the different extraction methods are given. It shows that with methods “cross-flow” and “resolve and precipitate,” the lowest DEHP concentration can be obtained at 63 ppm and 69 ppm after six extraction steps. The 0.1 % REACH threshold for DEHP can be reached in both extraction methods after four repetitions, whereas five repetitions are needed for the “counter-flow” method. As the previous paragraph stated, the “resolve and precipitate” method has the disadvantage of increased inclusion of solvent in the PVC gel, which leads to higher demand for drying energy and more heating time for re-dissolving; this method is less economical. Although the “counter-flow” method requires more extractions because of the re-use of the extracts from the batch before (the first three extracts are going to be regenerated, and the last two extracts are going to be used for the subsequent extraction), the solvent consumption is reduced (Fig. 5a). Considering the process economy, a “counter-flow” extraction is preferable.

3.5. Purification efficiency compared to legal threshold

In Fig. 5b and c, the extraction of other phthalates than DEHP has been investigated with the extraction methods “cross-flow” and “counter-flow.” Because the extraction methods “cross-flow” and “resolve+precipitate” have similar results, we focused here only on the “cross-flow” method. Besides DEHP, restricted phthalates BBP and DIBP are present in the PVC flooring waste with concentrations beyond the REACH threshold of 0.1 % (w/w). The restricted phthalates have been eliminated through both extraction methods, with “cross-flow” after two extractions and “counter-flow” after three. DBP is the only restricted phthalate in PVC flooring waste that is beneath the REACH limitations. These results reflect the former production volumes of phthalates, where DEHP had the largest share of the phthalate market (Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2011). Both extraction methods made reducing the total phthalate content beneath 1000 ppm possible. Considering the results of Fig. 5a, the “counter-flow” method uses less solvent and thus saves energy and material costs. Accordingly, this method is to be preferred.

3.6. Scale-up of DEHP extraction

Once the process parameters for the extraction of DEHP have been set through the laboratory experiments ($\theta <$ flashpoint of CreaSolv® solvent, powdery precipitation, < 15 min extraction time, counter-flow), the process has been up-scaled to a small technical scale of 5 kg/d. The extraction at this scale was performed in counter-flow with the re-use of solvent to safe solvent and energy. The results are shown in Fig. 5d. DEHP was therefore eliminated successfully when the laboratory process was scaled up. It could also be shown that the REACH threshold could be met after four extraction steps. The DEHP concentration in the extracts was higher at the technical scale compared to the laboratory-

Fig. 5. a) Decrease of DEHP concentration (in ppm) in PVC waste chips from flooring through three different extraction methods within DBR; purification step 0 = initial DEHP concentration; b) extraction of all banned phthalates via "cross-flow" extraction; c) extraction of all banned phthalates via "counter-flow" extraction; d) comparison of DEHP concentration in extracts of laboratory experiment and technical scale experiment; e) prediction model with lab data and m generated initial concentrations manifold to the lab data.

scale process due to the re-use of the DEHP-loaded solvent/precipitant composite.

The operation of the DBR in counter-current flow mode reduced the consumption of solvent and precipitant by 1/3 compared to the lab-scale experiments, thus reducing the overall costs.

Future development of the process will focus on automation and efficient drying of the polymer to keep the process energy consumption and overall costs to a minimum.

3.7. Prediction of needed extraction steps at different initial concentrations

Based on the laboratory tests, a prediction tool on a basis of a mathematical formula has been set up to predict the extraction steps necessary to reach the REACH threshold for phthalates of 1000 ppm by different initial DEHP concentrations.

Therefore, the decrease of the DEHP concentration per extraction step has been plotted (Fig. 5e), and an exponential curve has been obtained with the following equation:

$$c = c_0 * e^{-zn}$$

c DEHP concentration in ppm

c_0 initial DEHP concentration of PVC waste in ppm

z rate of decrease of DEHP

n number of extraction steps

Simplified assumed that the rate of decline remains the same for each extraction (in real terms, precipitation has a higher decrease than post-purification), the number of extraction steps required to reach the threshold can now be calculated by inserting the existing starting concentration c_0 of the waste input and the REACH threshold $c = 1000$ ppm. Different initial DEHP concentrations as a start concentration for the extraction have been tested and plotted (Fig. 5e). Three to four

extraction steps are needed between the DEHP concentration levels of 30,000 and 250,000 ppm to fulfill the legal threshold. This prediction is important for production on an industrial scale, as waste is always very inhomogeneous and fluctuations in DEHP concentration are to be expected. The formula is based on the data from the previous tests and only applies to the extraction parameters from the up-scale test.

4. Conclusion

Currently, there is only one acceptable and economically significant waste management strategy for plasticized PVC waste. This strategy is processing in an incineration plant, but this recovers only part of the energy used to manufacture the PVC, and the structure is destroyed. An alternative and promising route constitutes the DBR technique. With this, the macromolecular structure of PVC remains unchanged, and legacy additives are removed. In the course of prohibitions through the Basel Convention, Stockholm Convention, or REACH, today, an increasing demand for a closed-loop economy of hazardous waste is requested. An acceptable solution constitutes the DBR, where hazardous substances are eliminated, decomposed, and recycled while the polymers are returned to the production cycle. Therefore, it offers the potential of a similar recycling route in compliance with legal requirements for contaminated PVC waste.

This study describes the process development of the DBR of PVC flooring waste that has reached a mature level of TRL 5 and requires further upscale to bring such to an industrial level. In previous studies, we have shown that DBR can be used to recycle expanded polystyrene (EPS, from thermal insulation systems) contaminated with HBCD (REACH listed) (Schlummer et al., 2016). The German government has already confirmed that DBR can be used as an official treatment for EPS in addition to incineration (Umweltbundesamt, 2016). Consequently, the first industrial plant for recycling brominated EPS via dissolution-based technique was built and started up in the Netherlands at a demonstration level (TRL 7) and a capacity of 3300 t/y. Two other

process demonstrators (Indonesia, Germany) for DBR of polyolefins from multi-layered packaging have been built up. The technical and economic feasibility of the PVC flooring waste is also to be demonstrated (at TRL 6) by a demonstrator as part of the EU Horizon 2020-funded Circular Flooring project.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S. Wagner: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **M. Schlummer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107889](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107889).

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